

Towards a Unified Picture of Everything

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The quest to unify all knowledge has kept man restless for long. This is exemplified in Albert Einstein's quest for a unified field theory. In this note¹, the authors propose a novel way for man to understand nature in toto. They consider problems in general relativity and quantum mechanics and provide an equivalence between them. The equivalence is provided by noting that in general relativity the potential defines the metric which allows distance computations whereas in quantum mechanics the potential defines the probability of finding the particle at a particular location, some distance from the origin. However, a probability is nothing but a length or distance as per measure theory. Thus the two theories are linked in a novel manner. The chief remaining considerations are of scale and domain of applicability, and these need to be addressed.

To support this equivalence or link, ongoing work in our research enterprise will provide the mathematical formalism as well as Gedanken examples that illustrate the applicability of the new theory.

¹This note contains forward-looking statements and must be taken as a report of a work in progress.